

Towards a Conception and the Implementation of FAIR Data Management Tools for the Energy Domain

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FAIR Data Management [11] Motivation and Goals

- Ontologies as basis for metadata
- Tool and software support for
 - searching for research data*
 - FAIR data access*
 - creating new metadata types/schemas*
 - data publication*
 - integration of standards*
- Generic data access, serialization, and user interfaces

[11] Collins, S. et al.: Turning FAIR data into reality, 2018
[12] De Smedt, K. et al.: FAIR Digital Objects for Science – From Data Pieces to Actionable Knowledge Units, 2020

FAIR Digital Objects

- PID system according to the Handle System [9]
- PIDs without domain semantics
- Class FAIRDigitalObject; class hierarchy with abstract root class
- Class DataRegistryEntry references the research data and contains administrative metadata

[9] Kahn, R., Wilensky, R.: A framework for distributed digital object services. 2006

First Use Case: PV System [10]

- Proprietary PV ontology
- FDOs for research data and metadata objects
- Standards IEC 61850, GeoJSON, and SensorML integrated

[10] Schweikert, J. et al.: A photovoltaic system model integrating fair digital objects and ontologie. 2022

Ontologies and Conceptual Models

- Ontologies are generic in the sense of being application-independent [3]
- Conceptual models are application-specific and implementation-oriented [3][4]
- Ontologies and conceptual models are associated [4]
- Gomez-Perez et al. [11] recommend building ontologies on Conceptual Models
- Newer work shows efforts in ontology-driven Conceptual Modeling (e.g. [12])
- Both, conceptual models and ontologies describe classes and their relationships
- Descriptive and structural metadata are part of a knowledge graph
- Software defines and implements methods that change the knowledge graph objects

[3] Jarrar, M. et al.: On using conceptual data modeling for ontology engineering, 2003
[4] Kogalovsky, M.R., Kalinichenko, L.A.: Conceptual and ontological modeling in information systems, 2009
[13] Gomez-Perez et al.: Towards a Method to Conceptualize Domain Ontologies, 2000
[14] Verdonck, M. et al.: Comparing traditional conceptual modeling with ontology-driven conceptual modeling: An empirical study, 2019

Outlook: Fair Data Space (WIP)

- All objects identified by PIDs (first step: simple PID system)
- Classes described by **Structural Metadata** → **Generic** user interfaces - data access - serialization
- Tools already used: OEP Databus, **InfluxMetadata Exporter** and Zeitgeist, RO-Crate Exporter
- FDOs only for research data
- Adaption of use case from [10] with standard integration

Presentation by
A. Schmidt; today
at 1300; session A3